

1. Introduction

This document describes a laboratory-scale dataset acquired on a five-level steel frame instrumented with **two sensor types** (accelerometers and resistive foil strain gauges) and **two sensor layouts** per sensor type (optimized by Efl algorithm and suboptimal). The dataset is intended for research and benchmarking in operational modal analysis (OMA), optimal sensor placement (OSP), and strain-based modal identification.

The test structure is a steel frame comprising five levels, as depicted in Figure 1. Each level consists of a 500 × 250 mm slab supported by two beams. The beams are built from T-profiles (base and height of 30 mm, thickness 4 mm), and the columns have a 30 × 2 mm rectangular cross-section. Beam-to-column joints are assembled using small angle brackets fastened with screws.

Figure 1. Steel frame before (left) and after (right) the instrumentation.

2. Instrumentation

The structure was instrumented with:

- Triaxial MEMS accelerometer modules (GY-61 incorporating ADXL335)
- Resistive foil strain gauges (FLAB-6-11, 120 Ω nominal resistance). Strain was measured via Wheatstone bridge (quarter-bridge) and digitized through HX711 modules (gain 128, 24-bit ADC).

Acquisition was performed with an Arduino MEGA microcontroller.

3. Signals

Processed time series for the four cases (optimal and suboptimal layouts for accelerometers and strain gauges) are provided in the repository (see “time_series/”), its properties summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Signals properties

	Accelerometers	Strain gauges
Units	m/s ²	ϵ
Sampling frequency [Hz]	207.19	70.57
Record length [s]	1000	708
Spike removal	No	Yes
Detrending	Yes	Yes
Band-pass filter	5th order Butterworth	5th order Butterworth
Band-pass cutoffs	0.25-36 Hz	0.25-36 Hz

Time series are provided as semicolon-separated plain-text files with a header row (e.g., t;channel_1;...;channel_8). The channel columns are ordered consistently with the “CHANNELS (SAP2000 MODEL)” section in the corresponding modal results file, which provides the SAP2000 DOF/element reference for each channel.

4. Sensor layouts

A general overview of the channel locations is provided in the **channels_locations.pdf** document. The exact SAP2000 location associated with each channel is reported in the file containing the identified modal properties (under the **CHANNELS** section), where each channel is defined by its SAP2000 DOF/element reference. The notation adopted is as follows:

- **Accelerometers (joint displacement DOFs):** <JointObject>_<Direction> where <Direction > is one of $\pm U1$, $\pm U2$, $\pm U3$, according to the SAP2000 local axis convention shown in Figure 2. For example, 27_-U1 denotes a channel located on **Joint Object 27, measuring on the negative U1 local axis.**
- **Strain gauges (frame element faces):** <FrameObject>.<FrameElement>_<Position> where <Position> is one of up, right, bottom, left, defined with respect to the local axes of the corresponding SAP2000 frame element (Figure 2). For example, 263.1_up denotes a strain gauge located on **Frame Object 263, mesh element 1, on the upper face** in the local coordinate system.

Figure 2. Local axes in SAP2000 and frame element faces.

5. Modal identification

The modal identification has been performed with MOVA software. COV-SSI algorithm has been used, with the following hyperparameters:

Table 2. COV-SSI algorithm

	Accelerometers	Strain gauges
Time lag [s]	2.688	2.678
Model order	2-80	2-80
Clustering	Hierarchical clustering	Hierarchical clustering
Min. Cluster size	8	10
Max. Cluster distance	0.03	0.06